

Dawn VIR Sequence report for Ceres Second Extension Elliptical (C2E) (vir_da944)

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ABSTRACT

This document constitutes the official flight operation report for the VIR (Visible and Infrared Mapping Spectrometer) instrument onboard the Dawn spacecraft, specifically covering the commanding and sequencing activities performed for the vir_da944 session. These operations were executed as part of the C2E phase.

The mission profile focused on the observational sequences for the characterization of the planetary body Ceres, aiming to map its mineralogical features and surface properties.

The report details the generation of the instrument's commanding sequences and the formal verification process. All sequences have been checked against the mission's flight and guideline rules within the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) framework. Furthermore, the VIR SASF files were successfully integrated with the sequences of the other onboard instruments to ensure system-level compatibility and resource management. The final integrated sequences were successfully uploaded and executed on the spacecraft during the scheduled vir_da944 window.

KEYWORDS

VIR • Spectral Instrument • Dawn NASA Mission

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References

- [1] M. de Sanctis *et al.*, "The VIR Spectrometer," *issr*, vol. 163, no. 1-4, pp. 329-369, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11214-010-9668-5.
- [2] A. K. J. Stipanuk, "Spacecraft Activity Sequence File (SASF) Interface.," *Deep Space Mission System (DSMS) Subsystem Software Interface Specification*, 2004.

1. Check list of the sequence vir_c2e_C3S10LOW.r04.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_c2e_C3S10LOW.r04.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

1.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_c2e_c3s10LOW.r04.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_C2E_YMLSTART_C3S10LOW	588472982	588472984	2
VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_069	588473042	588473463	421
VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_069	588473642	588483548	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S10OpenCover_069	588484502	588484542	40
VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_069	588484622	588485644	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_069	588485647	588485685	38
VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_069	588485767	588485774	7
VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_069	588485827	588489427	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_069	588489427	588489727	300
VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_070	588569051	588569472	421
VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_070	588569651	588579557	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S10CalibrationDump_070	588580511	588582325	1814
VIR_C2E_C3S10OpenCover_070	588582611	588582651	40
VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_070	588582731	588583753	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_070	588583756	588583794	38
VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_070	588583876	588583883	7
VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_070	588583936	588587536	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_070	588587536	588587836	300
VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_071	588670353	588670774	421
VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_071	588670953	588680859	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S10OpenCover_071	588681813	588681853	40
VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_071	588681933	588682955	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_071	588682958	588682996	38
VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_071	588683078	588683085	7
VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_071	588683198	588686798	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_071	588686798	588687098	300
VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_072	588768472	588768893	421
VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_072	588769072	588778978	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S10OpenCover_072	588779932	588779972	40
VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_072	588780052	588781074	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_072	588781077	588781115	38
VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_072	588781197	588781204	7
VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_072	588781317	588784917	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_072	588784917	588785217	300
VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_073	588865792	588866213	421
VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_073	588866392	588876298	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S10OpenCover_073	588877252	588877292	40
VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_073	588877372	588878394	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_073	588878397	588878435	38
VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_073	588878517	588878524	7

VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_073	588878577	588882177	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_073	588882597	588882897	300
VIR_C2E_VMLEND_C3S10LOW	588882957	588882958	1

1.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

2. Check list of the sequence vir_c2e_C3S7LOW.r05.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_c2e_C3S7LOW.r05.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

2.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_c2e_c3s7LOW.r05.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_C2E_VMLSTART_C3S7LOW	586719679	586719681	2
VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOn_051	586719739	586720160	421
VIR_C2E_C3S7Standby_051	586720339	586720344	5
VIR_C2E_C3S7OpenCover_051	586720399	586720439	40
VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_051	586720519	586725051	4532
VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_051	586725139	586725177	38
VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_051	586725319	586729819	4500
VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_051	586729819	586730119	300
VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOn_052	586805583	586806004	421
VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOn_052	586806183	586816089	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S7CalibrationDump_052	586817043	586818857	1814
VIR_C2E_C3S7OpenCover_052	586819143	586819183	40
VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_052	586819263	586820285	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_052	586820288	586820326	38
VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOff_052	586820408	586820415	7
VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_052	586820468	586824068	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_052	586824068	586824368	300
VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOn_053	586906049	586906470	421
VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOn_053	586906649	586916555	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S7OpenCover_053	586917389	586917429	40
VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_053	586917509	586918531	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_053	586918534	586918572	38
VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOff_053	586918654	586918661	7
VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_053	586918714	586922014	3300
VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_053	586922014	586922314	300
VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOn_055	587100123	587100544	421
VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOn_055	587100723	587110629	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S7OpenCover_055	587111583	587111623	40
VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_055	587111703	587112725	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_055	587112728	587112766	38
VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOff_055	587112848	587112855	7
VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_055	587112908	587116508	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_055	587116568	587116868	300
VIR_C2E_VMLEND_C3S7LOW	587116928	587116929	1

2.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

SAFE
 MM_DUMP
 ANNEALING
 CALIB
 COOL_DOWN
 SCIENCE
 STAND_BY
 x 10⁹

SAFE
 MM_DUMP
 ANNEALING
 CALIB
 COOL_DOWN
 SCIENCE
 STAND_BY
 x 10⁹

3. Check list of the sequence vir_c2e_C3S8LOW.r03.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_c2e_C3S8LOW.r03.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

3.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_c2e_C3S8LOW.r03.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_C2E_YMLSTART_C3S8LOW	587293520	587293522	2
VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_057	587293580	587294001	421
VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOn_057	587294180	587304086	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S8CalibrationDump_057	587305040	587306854	1814
VIR_C2E_C3S8OpenCover_057	587307140	587307180	40
VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_057	587307260	587308282	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_057	587308285	587308323	38
VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_057	587308405	587308412	7
VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_057	587308525	587312125	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_057	587312125	587312425	300
VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_058	587393655	587394076	421
VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOn_058	587394255	587404161	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S8OpenCover_058	587405115	587405155	40
VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_058	587405235	587406257	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_058	587406260	587406298	38
VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_058	587406380	587406387	7
VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_058	587406500	587410100	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_058	587410100	587410400	300
VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_059	587491682	587492103	421
VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOn_059	587492282	587502188	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S8OpenCover_059	587503142	587503182	40
VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_059	587503262	587504284	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_059	587504287	587504325	38
VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_059	587504407	587504414	7
VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_059	587504527	587508127	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_059	587508127	587508427	300
VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_060	587589863	587590284	421
VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOn_060	587590463	587600369	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S8OpenCover_060	587601323	587601363	40
VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_060	587601443	587602465	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_060	587602468	587602506	38
VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_060	587602588	587602595	7
VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_060	587602708	587606308	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_060	587606308	587606608	300
VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_061	587688023	587688444	421
VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOn_061	587688623	587698529	9906
VIR_C2E_C3S8OpenCover_061	587699483	587699523	40
VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_061	587699603	587700625	1022
VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_061	587700628	587700666	38
VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_061	587700778	587700785	7

VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_O61	587700838	587704438	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_O61	587704438	587704738	300
VIR_C2E_VMLEND_C3S8LOW	587704798	587704799	1

3.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

4. Check list of the sequence vir_c2e_C3S9LOW.r02.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_c2e_C3S9LOW.r02.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

4.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_c2e_C359LOW.r02.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_C2E_YMLSTART_C359LOW	587884154	587884156	2
VIR_C2E_C359PowerOn_063	587884214	587884635	421
VIR_C2E_C359CryocoolerOn_063	587884814	587894720	9906
VIR_C2E_C359OpenCover_063	587895674	587895714	40
VIR_C2E_C359PushbroomToVIR_063	587895794	587896816	1022
VIR_C2E_C359CloseCover_063	587896819	587896857	38
VIR_C2E_C359CryocoolerOff_063	587896939	587896946	7
VIR_C2E_C359DumpDataToVR4_063	587896999	587900599	3600
VIR_C2E_C359PowerOff_063	587900599	587900899	300
VIR_C2E_C359PowerOn_064	587980127	587980548	421
VIR_C2E_C359CryocoolerOn_064	587980727	587990633	9906
VIR_C2E_C359CalibrationDump_064	587991587	587993401	1814
VIR_C2E_C359OpenCover_064	587993687	587993727	40
VIR_C2E_C359PushbroomToVIR_064	587993807	587994829	1022
VIR_C2E_C359CloseCover_064	587994832	587994870	38
VIR_C2E_C359CryocoolerOff_064	587994952	587994959	7
VIR_C2E_C359DumpDataToVR4_064	587995012	587998612	3600
VIR_C2E_C359PowerOff_064	587998612	587998812	300
VIR_C2E_C359PowerOn_065	588080268	588080689	421
VIR_C2E_C359CryocoolerOn_065	588080868	588090774	9906
VIR_C2E_C359OpenCover_065	588091728	588091768	40
VIR_C2E_C359PushbroomToVIR_065	588091848	588092870	1022
VIR_C2E_C359CloseCover_065	588092873	588092911	38
VIR_C2E_C359CryocoolerOff_065	588092963	588092970	7
VIR_C2E_C359DumpDataToVR4_065	588093023	588096623	3600
VIR_C2E_C359PowerOff_065	588096623	588096923	300
VIR_C2E_C359PowerOn_066	588178251	588178672	421
VIR_C2E_C359CryocoolerOn_066	588178851	588188757	9906
VIR_C2E_C359OpenCover_066	588189711	588189751	40
VIR_C2E_C359PushbroomToVIR_066	588189831	588190853	1022
VIR_C2E_C359CloseCover_066	588190856	588190894	38
VIR_C2E_C359CryocoolerOff_066	588190946	588190953	7
VIR_C2E_C359DumpDataToVR4_066	588191006	588194606	3600
VIR_C2E_C359PowerOff_066	588194606	588194906	300
VIR_C2E_C359PowerOn_067	588276230	588276651	421
VIR_C2E_C359CryocoolerOn_067	588276830	588286736	9906
VIR_C2E_C359OpenCover_067	588287690	588287730	40
VIR_C2E_C359PushbroomToVIR_067	588287810	588288832	1022
VIR_C2E_C359CloseCover_067	588288835	588288873	38
VIR_C2E_C359CryocoolerOff_067	588288925	588288932	7

VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_O67	588288985	588292585	3600
VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_O67	588301200	588301500	300
VIR_C2E_VMLEND_C3S9LOW	588301560	588301561	1

4.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

5. Integrated sequence: da944c.00.filter.rsoe

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the da944c.00.filter.rsoe sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

The VIR instrument was configured to acquire 8 calibration cubes and 18 cubes for IR channel and 1 for VIS channel.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
✓	□	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
✓	□	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	□	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
✓	□	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need

6. Appendix

This appendix contains the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) sequences referenced in this report, along with the SPICE meta-kernel employed for the geometric computations and reference frame transformations.

The following SASF files were processed:

6.1 The sequence: vir_c2e_C3S10LOW.r04.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_c2e_C3S10LOW.r04.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2018-216T23:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2018-244T05:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2018-207T06:49:13.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_c2e_C3S10LOW.r04;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT    DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR   sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE       Thu Jul 26 06:49:13 2018
20 *SEQGEN     V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN      2018-216T23:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF     2018-244T05:00:00.000
23 *TITLE      VIR_C2E_DA944_ds671
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *C2E_PERIAP_069, 2018-237T15:47:42.000
26 *C2E_PERIAP_070, 2018-238T19:01:51.000
27 *C2E_PERIAP_071, 2018-239T22:15:33.000
28 *C2E_PERIAP_072, 2018-241T01:28:52.000
29 *C2E_PERIAP_073, 2018-242T04:41:52.000
30 *EPOCHS_END
31 *Input files used:
32 *File Type Last modified      File name
33 *****
34 $$EOH
35 $$EOD
36
37 request(VIR_C2E_VMLSTART_C3S10LOW,
38         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_069-03:04:40,
39         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_c2e_C3S10LOW (ds671)",
40         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
41         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
42         KEY, "No_Key")
43
44     activity(1,
45             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
46
47             SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","ds671","ds671.mc
48             fb05")
49         ),
50     note(1,
51         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
52         TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds671 - vir_c2e_C3S10LOW"\
53     ),
54 end;

```

```
53
54 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10Power0n_069,
55         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_069-03:03:40,
56         TITLE, "VIR Power on",
57         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
58         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
59         KEY, "No_Key")
60
61     spawn(1,
62         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
63         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
64         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
65     ),
66     note(1,
67         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
68         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10Power0n_069: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
69     ),
70 end;
71
72 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10Cryocooler0n_069,
73         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_069-02:53:40,
74         TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
75         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
76         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
77         KEY, "No_Key")
78
79     command(1,
80         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
81         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10Cryocooler0n_069: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
82         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
83     ),
84     command(2,
85         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
86         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10Cryocooler0n_069: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
87         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
88     ),
89     note(1,
90         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
91         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10Cryocooler0n_069: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3
92         hour waiting."\"
93     ),
94 end;
95 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10openCover_069,
96         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_069+00:07:20,
97         TITLE, "VIR open cover",
98         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
99         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
100        KEY, "No_Key")
101
102     activity(1,
103         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
104         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10openCover_069: Set for opening the cover."\",
105         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
106     ),
107 end;
108
```

```
109 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_069,  
110     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_069+00:09:20,  
111     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",  
112     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
113     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
114     KEY, "No_Key")  
115  
116     command(1,  
117         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
118         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_069: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1  
119         detector,195 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,  
120         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI  
121     ),  
122     command(2,  
123         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
124         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,  
125         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_069: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
126         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
127     ),  
128     command(3,  
129         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
130         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_069: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
131         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
132     ),  
133     note(1,  
134         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
135         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_069: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit"\  
136     ),  
137 end;  
138 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_069,  
139     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_069+00:26:25,  
140     TITLE, "VIR close cover",  
141     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
142     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
143     KEY, "No_Key")  
144  
145     activity(1,  
146         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
147         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_069: Set for closing the cover."\  
148         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")  
149     ),  
150 end;  
151  
152 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_069,  
153     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_069+00:28:25,  
154     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",  
155     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
156     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
157     KEY, "No_Key")  
158  
159     command(1,  
160         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
161         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_069: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
162         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
163     ),  
164     command(2,
```

```

165     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
166     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_069: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\,
167     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
168 ),
169     note(1,
170         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
171         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_069: the cryocooling is off."\
172     ),
173 end;
174
175 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_069,
176     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_069+00:29:25,
177     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
178     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
179     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
180     KEY, "No_Key")
181
182     command(1,
183         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
184         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
185         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_069: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
186         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
187     ),
188     command(2,
189         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
190         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_069: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
191         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
192     ),
193     note(1,
194         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
195         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_069: data volume in VR4 0.350 Gibit."\
196     ),
197 end;
198
199 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_069,
200     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_069+01:29:25,
201     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
202     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
203     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
204     KEY, "No_Key")
205
206     note(1,
207         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
208         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_069: Power off VIR instrument."\
209     ),
210     spawn(1,
211         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
212         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE\,
213         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
214     ),
215     note(2,
216         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
217         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_069: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
218     ),
219 end;
220
221 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_070,

```

```

222     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_070-03:37:40,
223     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
224     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
225     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
226     KEY, "No_Key")
227
228     spawn(1,
229         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
230         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
231         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
232     ),
233     note(1,
234         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
235         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10Power0n_070: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
236     ),
237 end;
238
239 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10Cryocooler0n_070,
240     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_070-03:27:40,
241     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
242     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
243     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
244     KEY, "No_Key")
245
246     command(1,
247         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
248         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10Cryocooler0n_070: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
249         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
250     ),
251     command(2,
252         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
253         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10Cryocooler0n_070: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
254         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
255     ),
256     note(1,
257         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
258         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10Cryocooler0n_070: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3
259         hour waiting."\"
260     ),
261 end;
262 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CalibrationDump_070,
263     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_070-00:26:40,
264     TITLE, "VIR full calibration sequence",
265     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
266     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
267     KEY, "No_Key")
268
269     command(1,
270         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
271         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CalibrationDump_070: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\",
272         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
273     ),
274     command(2,
275         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
276         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CalibrationDump_070: perform the internal full calibration"\",
277         VIR_CALIBRATION("H_SPE_H_SPA_F","CLOSECOVERATEND","FULLCALSEQ")

```

```

278     ),
279     command(3,
280         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
281         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CalibrationDump_070: select VIR on 1553 bus"\,
282         XB_SELECT_INSTRUMENT("VIR")
283     ),
284     command(4,
285         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:02\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
286         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CalibrationDump_070: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
287         VIR_MM_DUMP("NO_COMPRESSION")
288     ),
289     command(5,
290         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
291         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CalibrationDump_070: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
292         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
293     ),
294     note(1,
295         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
296         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CalibrationDump_070: full calibration is finished."\",
297     ),
298     note(2,
299         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
300         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CalibrationDump_070: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit, 120 pages, 15960
301         packets."\",
302     ),
303
304     request(VIR_C2E_C3S10openCover_070,
305         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_070+00:08:20,
306         TITLE, "VIR open cover",
307         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
308         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
309         KEY, "No_Key")
310
311     activity(1,
312         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
313         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10openCover_070: Set for opening the cover."\",
314         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
315     ),
316 end;
317
318     request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_070,
319         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_070+00:10:20,
320         TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
321         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
322         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
323         KEY, "No_Key")
324
325     command(1,
326         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
327         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_070: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1
328         detector,195 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,
329         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
330     ),
331     command(2,
332         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
333         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,

```

```
333     NTEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_070: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
334     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
335   ),
336   command(3,
337     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:16:51\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
338     NTEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_070: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
339     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
340   ),
341   note(1,
342     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
343     TEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_070: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit\"\\
344   ),
345 end;
346
347 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_070,
348   START_TIME, C2E_PERIAP_070+00:27:25,
349   TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
350   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
351   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
352   KEY, \"No_Key\")
353
354   activity(1,
355     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:00\\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
356     NTEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_070: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
357     VIR_Cover(vir_cover, \"CLOSE\")
358   ),
359 end;
360
361 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_070,
362   START_TIME, C2E_PERIAP_070+00:29:25,
363   TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",
364   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
365   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
366   KEY, \"No_Key\")
367
368   command(1,
369     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:00\\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
370     NTEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_070: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
371     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
372   ),
373   command(2,
374     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
375     NTEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_070: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
376     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\", 75, 2500)
377   ),
378   note(1,
379     SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:01\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
380     TEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_070: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
381   ),
382 end;
383
384 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_070,
385   START_TIME, C2E_PERIAP_070+00:30:25,
386   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
387   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
388   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
389   KEY, \"No_Key\")
```

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390
391     command(1,
392         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
393         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
394         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_070: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
395         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
396     ),
397     command(2,
398         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
399         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_070: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
400         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
401     ),
402     note(1,
403         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
404         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_070: data volume in VR4 0.826 Gibit."\
405     ),
406 end;
407
408 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_070,
409     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_070+01:30:25,
410     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
411     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
412     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
413     KEY, "No_Key")
414
415     note(1,
416         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
417         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_070: Power off VIR instrument."\
418     ),
419     spawn(1,
420         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
421         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
422         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
423     ),
424     note(2,
425         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
426         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_070: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
427     ),
428 end;
429
430 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_071,
431     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_071-02:43:00,
432     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
433     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
434     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
435     KEY, "No_Key")
436
437     spawn(1,
438         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
439         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
440         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
441     ),
442     note(1,
443         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
444         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_071: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
445     ),
446 end;
```

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447
448 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_071,
449     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_071-02:33:00,
450     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
451     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
452     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
453     KEY, "No_Key")
454
455     command(1,
456         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
457         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_071: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
458         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
459     ),
460     command(2,
461         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
462         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_071: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN." \,
463         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
464     ),
465     note(1,
466         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
467         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_071: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3
468         hour waiting." \
469     ),
470 end;
471
472 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10openCover_071,
473     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_071+00:28:00,
474     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
475     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
476     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
477     KEY, "No_Key")
478
479     activity(1,
480         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
481         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10openCover_071: Set for opening the cover." \,
482         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
483     ),
484 end;
485
486 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_071,
487     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_071+00:30:00,
488     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
489     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
490     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
491     KEY, "No_Key")
492
493     command(1,
494         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
495         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_071: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1
496         detector,195 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s" \,
497         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
498     ),
499     command(2,
500         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
501         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000" \,
502         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_071: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
503         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")

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502     ),
503     command(3,
504         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
505         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_071: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
506         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
507     ),
508     note(1,
509         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
510         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_071: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit\"\\
511     ),
512 end;
513
514 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_071,
515     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_071+00:47:05,
516     TITLE, \"VIR cclose cover\",
517     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
518     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
519     KEY, \"No_Key\")
520
521     activity(1,
522         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
523         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_071: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
524         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
525     ),
526 end;
527
528 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_071,
529     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_071+00:49:05,
530     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",
531     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
532     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
533     KEY, \"No_Key\")
534
535     command(1,
536         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
537         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_071: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
538         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
539     ),
540     command(2,
541         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
542         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_071: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
543         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\",75,2500)
544     ),
545     note(1,
546         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
547         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_071: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
548     ),
549 end;
550
551 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_071,
552     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_071+00:51:05,
553     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
554     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
555     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
556     KEY, \"No_Key\")
557
558     command(1,
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559     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
560     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\  
561     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_071: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\  
562     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")  
563     ),  
564     command(2,  
565         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
566         NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_071: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
567         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
568     ),  
569     note(1,  
570         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
571         TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_071: data volume in VR4 1.176 Gibit.\"\  
572     ),  
573 end;  
574  
575 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_071,  
576     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_071+01:51:05,  
577     TITLE, \"VIR Power off\",  
578     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
579     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
580     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
581  
582     note(1,  
583         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
584         TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_071: Power off VIR instrument.\"\  
585     ),  
586     spawn(1,  
587         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
588         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\  
589         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)  
590     ),  
591     note(2,  
592         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
593         TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_071: Power off VML sequence is finished;\"\  
594     ),  
595 end;  
596  
597 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_072,  
598     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_072-02:41:00,  
599     TITLE, \"VIR Power on\",  
600     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
601     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
602     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
603  
604     spawn(1,  
605         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
606         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\  
607         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,\"VIR_P\",\"SAFE\")  
608     ),  
609     note(1,  
610         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
611         TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_072: Power on VML sequence is finished;\"\  
612     ),  
613 end;  
614  
615 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_072,
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616     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_072-02:31:00,
617     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
618     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
619     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
620     KEY, "No_Key")
621
622     command(1,
623     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
624     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_072: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
625     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
626     ),
627     command(2,
628     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
629     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_072: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN." \,
630     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
631     ),
632     note(1,
633     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
634     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_072: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3
        hour waiting." \
635     ),
636 end;
637
638 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10openCover_072,
639     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_072+00:30:00,
640     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
641     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
642     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
643     KEY, "No_Key")
644
645     activity(1,
646     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
647     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10openCover_072: Set for opening the cover." \,
648     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
649     ),
650 end;
651
652 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_072,
653     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_072+00:32:00,
654     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
655     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
656     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
657     KEY, "No_Key")
658
659     command(1,
660     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
661     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_072: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1
        detector,195 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s" \,
662     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195, "IR_ONLY", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 10, "NO_VI
663     ),
664     command(2,
665     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
666     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000" \,
667     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_072: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
668     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
669     ),
670     command(3,
    
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671     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
672     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_072: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
673     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
674   ),  
675   note(1,  
676     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
677     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_072: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit\"\\  
678   ),  
679 end;  
680  
681 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_072,  
682     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_072+00:49:05,  
683     TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",  
684     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
685     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
686     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
687  
688   activity(1,  
689     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
690     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_072: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,  
691     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")  
692   ),  
693 end;  
694  
695 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_072,  
696     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_072+00:51:05,  
697     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",  
698     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
699     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
700     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
701  
702   command(1,  
703     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
704     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_072: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
705     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
706   ),  
707   command(2,  
708     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
709     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_072: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,  
710     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\",75,2500)  
711   ),  
712   note(1,  
713     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
714     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_072: the cryocooling is off.\"\\  
715   ),  
716 end;  
717  
718 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_072,  
719     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_072+00:53:05,  
720     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",  
721     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
722     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
723     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
724  
725   command(1,  
726     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
727     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\\,
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728     NTEXT, \ "VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_072: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
729     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
730 ),
731     command(2,
732     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:59:54\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
733     NTEXT, \ "VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_072: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
734     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
735 ),
736     note(1,
737     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:05\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
738     TEXT, \ "VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_072: data volume in VR4 1.526 Gibit." \
739 ),
740 end;
741
742 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_072,
743     START_TIME, C2E_PERIAP_072+01:53:05,
744     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
745     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
746     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
747     KEY, "No_Key")
748
749     note(1,
750     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:00\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
751     TEXT, \ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_072: Power off VIR instrument." \
752 ),
753     spawn(1,
754     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:01\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
755     REQ_ENGINE_ID, \ANY_ENGINE\,
756     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
757 ),
758     note(2,
759     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:04:58\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
760     TEXT, \ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_072: Power off VML sequence is finished;" \
761 ),
762 end;
763
764 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_073,
765     START_TIME, C2E_PERIAP_073-02:52:00,
766     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
767     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
768     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
769     KEY, "No_Key")
770
771     spawn(1,
772     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:00:00\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
773     REQ_ENGINE_ID, \ANY_ENGINE\,
774     RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on, "VIR_P", "SAFE")
775 ),
776     note(1,
777     SCHEDULED_TIME, \00:07:00\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
778     TEXT, \ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOn_073: Power on VML sequence is finished;" \
779 ),
780 end;
781
782 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOn_073,
783     START_TIME, C2E_PERIAP_073-02:42:00,
784     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
    
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785     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
786     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
787     KEY, "No_Key")
788
789     command(1,
790         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
791         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10Cryocooler0n_073: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
792         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
793     ),
794     command(2,
795         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
796         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10Cryocooler0n_073: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN." \,
797         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
798     ),
799     note(1,
800         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
801         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10Cryocooler0n_073: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3
            hour waiting." \
802     ),
803 end;
804
805 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10openCover_073,
806     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_073+00:19:00,
807     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
808     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
809     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
810     KEY, "No_Key")
811
812     activity(1,
813         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
814         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10openCover_073: Set for opening the cover." \,
815         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
816     ),
817 end;
818
819 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_073,
820     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_073+00:21:00,
821     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
822     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
823     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
824     KEY, "No_Key")
825
826     command(1,
827         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
828         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_073: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1
            detector,195 frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s" \,
829         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
830     ),
831     command(2,
832         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
833         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000" \,
834         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_073: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
835         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
836     ),
837     command(3,
838         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
839         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_073: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
    
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840     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
841   ),
842   note(1,
843     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
844     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10PushbroomToVIR_073: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit"\
845   ),
846 end;
847
848 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_073,
849   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_073+00:38:05,
850   TITLE, "VIR close cover",
851   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
852   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
853   KEY, "No_Key")
854
855   activity(1,
856     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
857     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CloseCover_073: Set for closing the cover."\,
858     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
859   ),
860 end;
861
862 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_073,
863   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_073+00:40:05,
864   TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
865   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
866   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
867   KEY, "No_Key")
868
869   command(1,
870     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
871     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_073: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
872     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
873   ),
874   command(2,
875     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
876     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_073: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\,
877     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
878   ),
879   note(1,
880     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
881     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10CryocoolerOff_073: the cryocooling is off."\
882   ),
883 end;
884
885 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_073,
886   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_073+00:41:05,
887   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
888   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
889   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
890   KEY, "No_Key")
891
892   command(1,
893     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
894     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
895     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_073: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
896     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
```

```

897     ),
898     command(2,
899         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
900         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_073: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
901         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
902     ),
903     note(1,
904         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
905         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10DumpDataToVR4_073: data volume in VR4 1.877 Gibit." \
906     ),
907 end;
908
909 request(VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_073,
910     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_073+01:48:05,
911     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
912     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
913     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
914     KEY, "No_Key")
915
916     note(1,
917         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
918         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_073: Power off VIR instrument." \
919     ),
920     spawn(1,
921         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
922         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE \,
923         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
924     ),
925     note(2,
926         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
927         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S10PowerOff_073: Power off VML sequence is finished;" \
928     ),
929 end;
930
931 request(VIR_C2E_VMLEND_C3S10LOW,
932     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_073+01:54:05,
933     TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_c2e_C3S10LOW (ds671)",
934     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
935     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
936     KEY, "No_Key")
937
938     note(1,
939         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
940         TEXT,\ "END OF SEQUENCE: ds671 - vir_c2e_C3S10LOW" \
941     ),
942 end;
943
944 $$EOF

```

The following SASF files were processed:

6.2 The sequence: vir_c2e_C3S7LOW.r05.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_c2e_C3S7LOW.r05.sasf;

```

sasf

```

6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2018-216T23:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2018-244T05:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2018-207T06:49:06.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_c2e_C3S7LOW.r05;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT    DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR   sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE       Thu Jul 26 06:49:06 2018
20 *SEQGEN     V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN      2018-216T23:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF     2018-244T05:00:00.000
23 *TITLE      VIR_C2E_DA944_ds662
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *C2E_PERIAP_051, 2018-217T05:42:19.000
26 *C2E_PERIAP_052, 2018-218T08:58:03.000
27 *C2E_PERIAP_053, 2018-219T12:12:29.000
28 *C2E_PERIAP_055, 2018-221T18:36:18.000
29 *EPOCHS_END
30 *Input files used:
31 *File Type  Last modified          File name
32 *****
33 $$EOH
34 $$EOD
35
36 request(VIR_C2E_VMLSTART_C3S7LOW,
37         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_051-00:01:00,
38         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_c2e_C3S7LOW (ds662)",
39         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
40         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
41         KEY, "No_Key")
42
43     activity(1,
44         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
45
46         SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","ds662","ds662.mc
47         fb04")
48     ),
49     note(1,
50         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
51         TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds662 - vir_c2e_C3S7LOW"\
52     ),
53 end;
54
55 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOn_051,
56         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_051+00:00:00,
57         TITLE, "VIR Power on",
58         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
59         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
60         KEY, "No_Key")
61
62     spawn(1,
63         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
    
```

```

62     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
63     RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
64   ),
65   note(1,
66     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
67     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOn_051: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
68   ),
69   end;
70
71   request(VIR_C2E_C3S7Standby_051,
72     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_051+00:10:00,
73     TITLE, "VIR Stand_By",
74     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
75     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
76     KEY, "No_Key")
77
78   command(1,
79     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
80     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7Standby_051: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
81     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
82   ),
83   end;
84
85   request(VIR_C2E_C3S70penCover_051,
86     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_051+00:11:00,
87     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
88     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
89     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
90     KEY, "No_Key")
91
92   activity(1,
93     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
94     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S70penCover_051: Set for opening the cover."\",
95     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
96   ),
97   end;
98
99   request(VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_051,
100     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_051+00:13:00,
101     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
102     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
103     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
104     KEY, "No_Key")
105
106   command(1,
107     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
108     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_051: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
109     frame,23 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.020s VIS=20.000s"\,
110     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",23,63,1,504,1000,5,195,"VIS_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"N
111   ),
112   command(2,
113     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
114     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=2.830"\,
115     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_051: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
116     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
117   ),
118   command(3,

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```
118     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:15:21\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
119     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_051: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
120     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
121     ),  
122     note(1,  
123     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
124     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_051: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit\"\  
125     ),  
126 end;  
127  
128 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_051,  
129     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_051+01:30:00,  
130     TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",  
131     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
132     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
133     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
134  
135     activity(1,  
136     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
137     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_051: Set for closing the cover.\"\  
138     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")  
139     ),  
140 end;  
141  
142 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_051,  
143     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_051+01:33:00,  
144     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",  
145     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
146     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
147     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
148  
149     command(1,  
150     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
151     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=0.353\"\  
152     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_051: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\  
153     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")  
154     ),  
155     command(2,  
156     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:14:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
157     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_051: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
158     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
159     ),  
160     note(1,  
161     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
162     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_051: data volume in VR4 0.124 Gibit.\"\  
163     ),  
164 end;  
165  
166 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_051,  
167     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_051+02:48:00,  
168     TITLE, \"VIR Power off\",  
169     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
170     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
171     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
172  
173     note(1,  
174     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
```

```
175     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_051: Power off VIR instrument."\
176   ),
177   spawn(1,
178     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
179     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
180     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
181   ),
182   note(2,
183     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
184     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_051: Power off VML sequence is finished;\"\
185   ),
186 end;
187
188 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOn_052,
189   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_052-03:25:00,
190   TITLE, "VIR Power on",
191   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
192   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
193   KEY, "No_Key")
194
195   spawn(1,
196     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
197     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
198     RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
199   ),
200   note(1,
201     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
202     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOn_052: Power on VML sequence is finished;\"\
203   ),
204 end;
205
206 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOn_052,
207   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_052-03:15:00,
208   TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
209   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
210   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
211   KEY, "No_Key")
212
213   command(1,
214     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
215     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOn_052: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\
216     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
217   ),
218   command(2,
219     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
220     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOn_052: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\
221     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
222   ),
223   note(1,
224     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
225     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOn_052: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
226     waiting."\
227   ),
228 end;
229
229 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7CalibrationDump_052,
230   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_052-00:14:00,
```

```
231     TITLE, "VIR full calibration sequence",
232     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
233     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
234     KEY, "No_Key")
235
236     command(1,
237         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
238         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CalibrationDump_052: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
239         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
240     ),
241     command(2,
242         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
243         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CalibrationDump_052: perform the internal full calibration"\,
244         VIR_CALIBRATION("H_SPE_H_SPA_F", "CLOSECOVERATEND", "FULLLALSEQ")
245     ),
246     command(3,
247         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
248         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CalibrationDump_052: select VIR on 1553 bus"\,
249         XB_SELECT_INSTRUMENT("VIR")
250     ),
251     command(4,
252         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:02\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
253         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CalibrationDump_052: begin data dumping into VR4.""\,
254         VIR_MM_DUMP("NO_COMPRESSION")
255     ),
256     command(5,
257         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
258         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CalibrationDump_052: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
259         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
260     ),
261     note(1,
262         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
263         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CalibrationDump_052: full calibration is finished.""\
264     ),
265     note(2,
266         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
267         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CalibrationDump_052: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit, 120 pages, 15960
268         packets.""\
269 end;
270
271 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7OpenCover_052,
272     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_052+00:21:00,
273     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
274     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
275     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
276     KEY, "No_Key")
277
278     activity(1,
279         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
280         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7OpenCover_052: Set for opening the cover.""\,
281         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
282     ),
283 end;
284
285 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_052,
286     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_052+00:23:00,
```

```
287     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
288     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
289     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
290     KEY, "No_Key")
291
292     command(1,
293     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
294     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_052: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,
295     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
296     ),
297     command(2,
298     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
299     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
300     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_052: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
301     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
302     ),
303     command(3,
304     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
305     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_052: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
306     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
307     ),
308     note(1,
309     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
310     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_052: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit"\
311     ),
312 end;
313
314 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_052,
315     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_052+00:40:05,
316     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
317     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
318     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
319     KEY, "No_Key")
320
321     activity(1,
322     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
323     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_052: Set for closing the cover.""\,
324     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
325     ),
326 end;
327
328 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0ff_052,
329     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_052+00:42:05,
330     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
331     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
332     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
333     KEY, "No_Key")
334
335     command(1,
336     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
337     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0ff_052: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
338     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
339     ),
340     command(2,
341     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
342     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0ff_052: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.""\,
```

```
343     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
344   ),
345   note(1,
346     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
347     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOff_052: the cryocooling is off."\
348   ),
349 end;
350
351 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_052,
352   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_052+00:43:05,
353   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
354   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
355   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
356   KEY, "No_Key")
357
358   command(1,
359     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
360     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
361     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_052: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
362     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
363   ),
364   command(2,
365     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
366     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_052: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
367     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
368   ),
369   note(1,
370     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
371     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_052: data volume in VR4 0.600 Gibit."\
372   ),
373 end;
374
375 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_052,
376   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_052+01:43:05,
377   TITLE, "VIR Power off",
378   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
379   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
380   KEY, "No_Key")
381
382   note(1,
383     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
384     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_052: Power off VIR instrument."\
385   ),
386   spawn(1,
387     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
388     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
389     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
390   ),
391   note(2,
392     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
393     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_052: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
394   ),
395 end;
396
397 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOn_053,
398   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_053-02:45:00,
399   TITLE, "VIR Power on",
```

```
400     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
401     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
402     KEY, "No_Key")
403
404     spawn(1,
405         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
406         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
407         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
408     ),
409     note(1,
410         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
411         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Power0n_053: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
412     ),
413 end;
414
415 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0n_053,
416     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_053-02:35:00,
417     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
418     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
419     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
420     KEY, "No_Key")
421
422     command(1,
423         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
424         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0n_053: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
425         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
426     ),
427     command(2,
428         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
429         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0n_053: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
430         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
431     ),
432     note(1,
433         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
434         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0n_053: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
435         waiting."\"
436     ),
437 end;
438 request(VIR_C2E_C3S70penCover_053,
439     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_053+00:24:00,
440     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
441     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
442     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
443     KEY, "No_Key")
444
445     activity(1,
446         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
447         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S70penCover_053: Set for opening the cover."\",
448         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
449     ),
450 end;
451
452 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_053,
453     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_053+00:26:00,
454     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
455     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
```

```

456     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
457     KEY, "No_Key")
458
459     command(1,
460     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
461     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_053: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,
462     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
463     ),
464     command(2,
465     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
466     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
467     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_053: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
468     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
469     ),
470     command(3,
471     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
472     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_053: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
473     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
474     ),
475     note(1,
476     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
477     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_053: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit"\
478     ),
479 end;
480
481 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_053,
482     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_053+00:43:05,
483     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
484     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
485     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
486     KEY, "No_Key")
487
488     activity(1,
489     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
490     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_053: Set for closing the cover.""\,
491     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
492     ),
493 end;
494
495 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0ff_053,
496     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_053+00:45:05,
497     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
498     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
499     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
500     KEY, "No_Key")
501
502     command(1,
503     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
504     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0ff_053: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
505     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
506     ),
507     command(2,
508     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
509     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0ff_053: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.""\,
510     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
511     ),

```

```
512     note(1,
513         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
514         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOff_053: the cryocooling is off.\"\
515     ),
516 end;
517
518 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_053,
519     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_053+00:46:05,
520     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
521     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
522     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
523     KEY, "No_Key")
524
525     command(1,
526         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
527         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
528         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_053: begin data dumping into VR4.\"",
529         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
530     ),
531     command(2,
532         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:54:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
533         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_053: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"",
534         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
535     ),
536     note(1,
537         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
538         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_053: data volume in VR4 0.950 Gibit.\"\
539     ),
540 end;
541
542 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_053,
543     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_053+01:41:05,
544     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
545     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
546     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
547     KEY, "No_Key")
548
549     note(1,
550         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
551         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_053: Power off VIR instrument.\"\
552     ),
553     spawn(1,
554         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
555         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
556         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
557     ),
558     note(2,
559         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
560         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOff_053: Power off VML sequence is finished;\"\
561     ),
562 end;
563
564 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7PowerOn_055,
565     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_055-03:14:15,
566     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
567     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
568     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
```

```
569     KEY, "No_Key")
570
571     spawn(1,
572         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
573         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
574         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
575     ),
576     note(1,
577         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
578         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Power0n_055: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
579     ),
580 end;
581
582 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0n_055,
583     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_055-03:04:15,
584     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
585     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
586     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
587     KEY, "No_Key")
588
589     command(1,
590         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
591         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0n_055: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
592         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
593     ),
594     command(2,
595         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
596         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0n_055: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
597         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
598     ),
599     note(1,
600         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
601         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0n_055: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
602         waiting."\<
603     ),
604 end;
605 request(VIR_C2E_C3S70penCover_055,
606     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_055-00:03:15,
607     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
608     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
609     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
610     KEY, "No_Key")
611
612     activity(1,
613         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
614         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S70penCover_055: Set for opening the cover."\",
615         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
616     ),
617 end;
618
619 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_055,
620     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_055-00:01:15,
621     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
622     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
623     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
624     KEY, "No_Key")
```

```

625
626     command(1,
627         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
628         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_055: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
        frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,
629         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
630     ),
631     command(2,
632         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
633         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
634         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_055: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
635         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
636     ),
637     command(3,
638         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
639         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_055: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
640         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
641     ),
642     note(1,
643         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
644         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7PushbroomToVIR_055: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit"\
645     ),
646 end;
647
648 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_055,
649     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_055+00:15:50,
650     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
651     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
652     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
653     KEY, "No_Key")
654
655     activity(1,
656         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
657         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CloseCover_055: Set for closing the cover.""\,
658         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
659     ),
660 end;
661
662 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOff_055,
663     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_055+00:17:50,
664     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
665     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
666     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
667     KEY, "No_Key")
668
669     command(1,
670         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
671         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOff_055: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
672         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
673     ),
674     command(2,
675         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
676         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S7CryocoolerOff_055: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.""\,
677         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
678     ),
679     note(1,
680         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
    
```

```
681     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7Cryocooler0ff_055: the cryocooling is off.\"\n682   ),\n683 end;\n684\n685 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_055,\n686     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_055+00:18:50,\n687     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",\n688     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",\n689     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",\n690     KEY, \"No_Key\")\n691\n692     command(1,\n693     SCHEDULED_TIME,\\"00:00:00\",FROM_REQUEST_START,\n694     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\", \n695     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_055: begin data dumping into VR4.\"", \n696     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")\n697   ),\n698   command(2,\n699     SCHEDULED_TIME,\\"00:59:54\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,\n700     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_055: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"", \n701     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()\n702   ),\n703   note(1,\n704     SCHEDULED_TIME,\\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,\n705     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7DumpDataToVR4_055: data volume in VR4 1.300 Gibit.\"", \n706   ),\n707 end;\n708\n709 request(VIR_C2E_C3S7Power0ff_055,\n710     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_055+01:19:50,\n711     TITLE, \"VIR Power off\",\n712     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",\n713     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",\n714     KEY, \"No_Key\")\n715\n716     note(1,\n717     SCHEDULED_TIME,\\"00:00:00\",FROM_REQUEST_START,\n718     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7Power0ff_055: Power off VIR instrument.\"", \n719   ),\n720     spawn(1,\n721     SCHEDULED_TIME,\\"00:00:01\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,\n722     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\\"ANY_ENGINE\", \n723     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)\n724   ),\n725     note(2,\n726     SCHEDULED_TIME,\\"00:04:58\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,\n727     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S7Power0ff_055: Power off VML sequence is finished;\"", \n728   ),\n729 end;\n730\n731 request(VIR_C2E_VMLEND_C3S7LOW,\n732     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_055+01:25:50,\n733     TITLE, \"VIR Sequence End - vir_c2e_C3S7LOW (ds662)\",\n734     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",\n735     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",\n736     KEY, \"No_Key\")\n737
```

```

738     note(1,
739         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
740         TEXT,\"END OF SEQUENCE: ds662 - vir_c2e_C3S7LOW\"
741     ),
742 end;
743
744 $$EOF
    
```

The following SASF files were processed:

6.3 The sequence: vir_c2e_C3S8LOW.r03.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_c2e_C3S8LOW.r03.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2018-216T23:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2018-244T05:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2018-185T06:45:49.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_c2e_C3S8LOW.r03;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN     SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT   DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR  sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE      Wed Jul 04 06:45:49 2018
20 *SEQGEN    V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN     2018-216T23:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF    2018-244T05:00:00.000
23 *TITLE     VIR_C2E_DA944_ds665
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *C2E_PERIAP_057, 2018-224T00:53:35.000
26 *C2E_PERIAP_058, 2018-225T04:06:30.000
27 *C2E_PERIAP_059, 2018-226T07:20:17.000
28 *C2E_PERIAP_060, 2018-227T10:34:38.000
29 *C2E_PERIAP_061, 2018-228T13:49:08.000
30 *EPOCHS_END
31 *Input files used:
32 *File Type Last modified      File name
33 *****
34 $$EOH
35 $$EOD
36
37 request(VIR_C2E_VMLSTART_C3S8LOW,
38         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_057-03:48:15,
39         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_c2e_C3S8LOW (ds665)",
40         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
41         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
42         KEY, "No_Key")
43
44     activity(1,
45         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
    
```

```
46     SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","ds665","ds665.mc
47     fb05")
48     ),
49     note(1,
50     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
51     TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds665 - vir_c2e_C3S8LOW"\
52     ),
53     end;
54     request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_057,
55     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_057-03:47:15,
56     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
57     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
58     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
59     KEY, "No_Key")
60
61     spawn(1,
62     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
63     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
64     RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
65     ),
66     note(1,
67     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
68     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_057: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
69     ),
70     end;
71
72     request(VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOn_057,
73     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_057-03:37:15,
74     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
75     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
76     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
77     KEY, "No_Key")
78
79     command(1,
80     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
81     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOn_057: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
82     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
83     ),
84     command(2,
85     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
86     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOn_057: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.""\,
87     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
88     ),
89     note(1,
90     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
91     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOn_057: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
92     waiting.""\
93     ),
94     end;
95     request(VIR_C2E_C3S8CalibrationDump_057,
96     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_057-00:36:15,
97     TITLE, "VIR full calibration sequence",
98     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
99     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
100    KEY, "No_Key")
```

```
101
102     command(1,
103         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
104         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CalibrationDump_057: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
105         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
106     ),
107     command(2,
108         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
109         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CalibrationDump_057: perform the internal full calibration"\,
110         VIR_CALIBRATION("H_SPE_H_SPA_F","CLOSECOVERATEND","FULLCALSEQ")
111     ),
112     command(3,
113         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
114         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CalibrationDump_057: select VIR on 1553 bus"\,
115         XB_SELECT_INSTRUMENT("VIR")
116     ),
117     command(4,
118         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:02\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
119         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CalibrationDump_057: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
120         VIR_MM_DUMP("NO_COMPRESSION")
121     ),
122     command(5,
123         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
124         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CalibrationDump_057: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
125         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
126     ),
127     note(1,
128         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
129         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CalibrationDump_057: full calibration is finished."\"
130     ),
131     note(2,
132         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
133         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CalibrationDump_057: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit, 120 pages, 15960
134         packets."\"
135     end;
136
137 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8OpenCover_057,
138     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_057-00:01:15,
139     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
140     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
141     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
142     KEY, "No_Key")
143
144     activity(1,
145         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
146         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8OpenCover_057: Set for opening the cover."\",
147         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
148     ),
149 end;
150
151 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_057,
152     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_057+00:00:45,
153     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
154     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
155     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
156     KEY, "No_Key")
```

```

157
158     command(1,
159         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
160         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_057: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
161         frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,
162         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
163     ),
164     command(2,
165         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
166         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
167         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_057: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
168         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
169     ),
170     command(3,
171         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
172         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_057: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
173         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
174     ),
175     note(1,
176         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
177         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_057: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit"\
178     ),
179 end;
180 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_057,
181     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_057+00:17:50,
182     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
183     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
184     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
185     KEY, "No_Key")
186
187     activity(1,
188         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
189         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_057: Set for closing the cover.""\,
190         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
191     ),
192 end;
193
194 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_057,
195     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_057+00:19:50,
196     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
197     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
198     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
199     KEY, "No_Key")
200
201     command(1,
202         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
203         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_057: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
204         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
205     ),
206     command(2,
207         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
208         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_057: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.""\,
209         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
210     ),
211     note(1,
212         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
    
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213     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_057: the cryocooling is off."\  
214     ),  
215 end;  
216  
217 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_057,  
218     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_057+00:21:50,  
219     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
220     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
221     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
222     KEY, "No_Key")  
223  
224     command(1,  
225     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
226     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\  
227     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_057: begin data dumping into VR4."\  
228     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")  
229     ),  
230     command(2,  
231     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
232     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_057: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
233     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
234     ),  
235     note(1,  
236     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
237     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_057: data volume in VR4 0.476 Gibit."\  
238     ),  
239 end;  
240  
241 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_057,  
242     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_057+01:21:50,  
243     TITLE, "VIR Power off",  
244     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
245     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
246     KEY, "No_Key")  
247  
248     note(1,  
249     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
250     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_057: Power off VIR instrument."\  
251     ),  
252     spawn(1,  
253     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
254     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE\  
255     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)  
256     ),  
257     note(2,  
258     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
259     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_057: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\  
260     ),  
261 end;  
262  
263 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_058,  
264     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_058-03:12:15,  
265     TITLE, "VIR Power on",  
266     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
267     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
268     KEY, "No_Key")  
269
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270     spawn(1,
271         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
272         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
273         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
274     ),
275     note(1,
276         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
277         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Power0n_058: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
278     ),
279 end;
280
281 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_058,
282     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_058-03:02:15,
283     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
284     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
285     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
286     KEY, "No_Key")
287
288     command(1,
289         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
290         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_058: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
291         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
292     ),
293     command(2,
294         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
295         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_058: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
296         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
297     ),
298     note(1,
299         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
300         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_058: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
301         waiting."\"
302     ),
303 end;
304
305 request(VIR_C2E_C3S80penCover_058,
306     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_058-00:01:15,
307     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
308     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
309     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
310     KEY, "No_Key")
311
312     activity(1,
313         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
314         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S80penCover_058: Set for opening the cover."\",
315         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
316     ),
317 end;
318
319 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_058,
320     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_058+00:00:45,
321     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
322     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
323     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
324     KEY, "No_Key")
325
326     command(1,
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326     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
327     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_058: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195  
frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,  
328     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI  
329     ),  
330     command(2,  
331     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
332     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,  
333     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_058: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,  
334     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
335     ),  
336     command(3,  
337     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
338     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_058: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
339     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
340     ),  
341     note(1,  
342     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
343     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_058: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit"\  
344     ),  
345 end;  
346  
347 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_058,  
348     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_058+00:17:50,  
349     TITLE, "VIR close cover",  
350     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
351     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
352     KEY, "No_Key")  
353  
354     activity(1,  
355     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
356     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_058: Set for closing the cover."\  
357     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")  
358     ),  
359 end;  
360  
361 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_058,  
362     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_058+00:19:50,  
363     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",  
364     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
365     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
366     KEY, "No_Key")  
367  
368     command(1,  
369     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
370     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_058: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
371     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
372     ),  
373     command(2,  
374     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
375     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_058: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\  
376     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)  
377     ),  
378     note(1,  
379     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
380     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CryocoolerOff_058: the cryocooling is off."\  
381     ),
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382 end;
383
384 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_058,
385         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_058+00:21:50,
386         TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
387         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
388         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
389         KEY, "No_Key")
390
391     command(1,
392         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
393         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
394         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_058: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
395         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
396     ),
397     command(2,
398         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
399         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_058: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
400         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
401     ),
402     note(1,
403         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
404         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_058: data volume in VR4 0.826 Gibit."\
405     ),
406 end;
407
408 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_058,
409         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_058+01:21:50,
410         TITLE, "VIR Power off",
411         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
412         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
413         KEY, "No_Key")
414
415     note(1,
416         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
417         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_058: Power off VIR instrument."\
418     ),
419     spawn(1,
420         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
421         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE\,
422         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
423     ),
424     note(2,
425         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
426         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_058: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
427     ),
428 end;
429
430 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_059,
431         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_059-03:12:15,
432         TITLE, "VIR Power on",
433         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
434         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
435         KEY, "No_Key")
436
437     spawn(1,
438         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
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439     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
440     RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
441   ),
442   note(1,
443     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
444     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_059: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
445   ),
446 end;
447
448 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_059,
449   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_059-03:02:15,
450   TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
451   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
452   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
453   KEY, "No_Key")
454
455   command(1,
456     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
457     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_059: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
458     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
459   ),
460   command(2,
461     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
462     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_059: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
463     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
464   ),
465   note(1,
466     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
467     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_059: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
468     waiting."\"
469   ),
470 end;
471
472 request(VIR_C2E_C3S80penCover_059,
473   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_059-00:01:15,
474   TITLE, "VIR open cover",
475   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
476   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
477   KEY, "No_Key")
478
479   activity(1,
480     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
481     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S80penCover_059: Set for opening the cover."\",
482     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
483   ),
484 end;
485
486 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_059,
487   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_059+00:00:45,
488   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
489   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
490   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
491   KEY, "No_Key")
492
493   command(1,
494     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
495     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_059: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
496     frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\"

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495     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
496 ),
497     command(2,
498     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
499     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
500     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_059: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
501     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
502 ),
503     command(3,
504     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
505     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_059: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
506     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
507 ),
508     note(1,
509     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
510     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_059: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit"\
511 ),
512 end;
513
514 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_059,
515     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_059+00:17:50,
516     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
517     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
518     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
519     KEY, "No_Key")
520
521     activity(1,
522     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
523     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_059: Set for closing the cover."\",
524     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
525 ),
526 end;
527
528 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_059,
529     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_059+00:19:50,
530     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
531     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
532     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
533     KEY, "No_Key")
534
535     command(1,
536     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
537     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_059: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
538     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
539 ),
540     command(2,
541     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
542     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_059: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\",
543     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
544 ),
545     note(1,
546     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
547     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_059: the cryocooling is off."\"
548 ),
549 end;
550
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551 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_059,
552     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_059+00:21:50,
553     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
554     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
555     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
556     KEY, "No_Key")
557
558     command(1,
559         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
560         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
561         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_059: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
562         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
563     ),
564     command(2,
565         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
566         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_059: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
567         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
568     ),
569     note(1,
570         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
571         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_059: data volume in VR4 1.176 Gibit."\
572     ),
573 end;
574
575 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_059,
576     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_059+01:21:50,
577     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
578     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
579     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
580     KEY, "No_Key")
581
582     note(1,
583         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
584         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_059: Power off VIR instrument."\
585     ),
586     spawn(1,
587         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
588         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE\,
589         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
590     ),
591     note(2,
592         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
593         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_059: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
594     ),
595 end;
596
597 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_060,
598     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_060-03:10:15,
599     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
600     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
601     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
602     KEY, "No_Key")
603
604     spawn(1,
605         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
606         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE\,
607         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on, "VIR_P", "SAFE")
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608     ),
609     note(1,
610         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
611         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8Power0n_060: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
612     ),
613 end;
614
615 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_060,
616     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_060-03:00:15,
617     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
618     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
619     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
620     KEY, "No_Key")
621
622     command(1,
623         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
624         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_060: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
625         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
626     ),
627     command(2,
628         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
629         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_060: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
630         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
631     ),
632     note(1,
633         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
634         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_060: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
        waiting."\"
635     ),
636 end;
637
638 request(VIR_C2E_C3S80penCover_060,
639     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_060+00:00:45,
640     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
641     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
642     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
643     KEY, "No_Key")
644
645     activity(1,
646         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
647         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S80penCover_060: Set for opening the cover."\",
648         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
649     ),
650 end;
651
652 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_060,
653     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_060+00:02:45,
654     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
655     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
656     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
657     KEY, "No_Key")
658
659     command(1,
660         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
661         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_060: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
        frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s\"\",
662         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
    
```

```
663     ),
664     command(2,
665         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
666         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\"\\,
667         NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_060: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
668         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
669     ),
670     command(3,
671         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
672         NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_060: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
673         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
674     ),
675     note(1,
676         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
677         TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_060: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit\"\\
678     ),
679 end;
680
681 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_060,
682     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_060+00:19:50,
683     TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
684     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
685     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
686     KEY, \"No_Key\")
687
688     activity(1,
689         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
690         NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_060: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
691         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
692     ),
693 end;
694
695 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_060,
696     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_060+00:21:50,
697     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",
698     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
699     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
700     KEY, \"No_Key\")
701
702     command(1,
703         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
704         NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_060: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
705         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
706     ),
707     command(2,
708         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
709         NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_060: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
710         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\",75,2500)
711     ),
712     note(1,
713         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
714         TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_060: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
715     ),
716 end;
717
718 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_060,
719     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_060+00:23:50,
```

```

720     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
721     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
722     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
723     KEY, "No_Key")
724
725     command(1,
726         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
727         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
728         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_060: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
729         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
730     ),
731     command(2,
732         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
733         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_060: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
734         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
735     ),
736     note(1,
737         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
738         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_060: data volume in VR4 1.526 Gibit."\
739     ),
740 end;
741
742 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_060,
743     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_060+01:23:50,
744     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
745     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
746     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
747     KEY, "No_Key")
748
749     note(1,
750         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
751         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_060: Power off VIR instrument."\
752     ),
753     spawn(1,
754         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
755         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE\,
756         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
757     ),
758     note(2,
759         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
760         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_060: Power off VML sequence is finished;"\
761     ),
762 end;
763
764 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_061,
765     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_061-03:08:45,
766     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
767     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
768     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
769     KEY, "No_Key")
770
771     spawn(1,
772         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
773         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ ANY_ENGINE\,
774         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
775     ),
776     note(1,

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777     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
778     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOn_061: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
779     ),
780 end;
781
782 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_061,
783     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_061-02:58:45,
784     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
785     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
786     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
787     KEY, "No_Key")
788
789     command(1,
790     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
791     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_061: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
792     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
793     ),
794     command(2,
795     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
796     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_061: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
797     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
798     ),
799     note(1,
800     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
801     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0n_061: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
802     waiting."\"
803     ),
804 end;
805
806 request(VIR_C2E_C3S80penCover_061,
807     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_061+00:02:15,
808     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
809     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
810     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
811     KEY, "No_Key")
812
813 activity(1,
814     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
815     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S80penCover_061: Set for opening the cover."\",
816     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
817     ),
818 end;
819
820 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_061,
821     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_061+00:04:15,
822     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
823     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
824     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
825     KEY, "No_Key")
826
827     command(1,
828     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
829     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_061: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
830     frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,
831     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI

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832     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
833     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000\"\\,
834     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_061: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
835     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
836 ),
837     command(3,
838     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
839     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_061: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
840     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
841 ),
842     note(1,
843     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
844     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PushbroomToVIR_061: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit\"\\
845 ),
846 end;
847
848 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_061,
849     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_061+00:21:20,
850     TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
851     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
852     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
853     KEY, \"No_Key\")
854
855     activity(1,
856     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
857     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8CloseCover_061: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,
858     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
859 ),
860 end;
861
862 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_061,
863     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_061+00:23:50,
864     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",
865     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
866     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
867     KEY, \"No_Key\")
868
869     command(1,
870     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
871     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_061: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
872     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
873 ),
874     command(2,
875     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
876     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_061: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
877     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\",75,2500)
878 ),
879     note(1,
880     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
881     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8Cryocooler0ff_061: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
882 ),
883 end;
884
885 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_061,
886     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_061+00:24:50,
887     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
888     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
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889     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
890     KEY, "No_Key")
891
892     command(1,
893     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
894     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\",
895     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_061: begin data dumping into VR4.\",
896     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
897     ),
898     command(2,
899     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
900     NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_061: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
901     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
902     ),
903     note(1,
904     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
905     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8DumpDataToVR4_061: data volume in VR4 1.877 Gibit.\",
906     ),
907 end;
908
909 request(VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_061,
910     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_061+01:24:50,
911     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
912     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
913     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
914     KEY, "No_Key")
915
916     note(1,
917     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
918     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_061: Power off VIR instrument.\",
919     ),
920     spawn(1,
921     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
922     REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
923     RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
924     ),
925     note(2,
926     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
927     TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S8PowerOff_061: Power off VML sequence is finished;\",
928     ),
929 end;
930
931 request(VIR_C2E_VMLEND_C3S8LOW,
932     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_061+01:30:50,
933     TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_c2e_C3S8LOW (ds665)",
934     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
935     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
936     KEY, "No_Key")
937
938     note(1,
939     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
940     TEXT,\"END OF SEQUENCE: ds665 - vir_c2e_C3S8LOW\",
941     ),
942 end;
943
944 $$EOF

```

The following SASF files were processed:

6.4 The sequence: vir_c2e_C3S9LOW.r02.sasf

```

1  CCSD3ZF000010000001NJPL3KS0L015$$MARK$$;
2  MISSION_NAME = DAWN;
3  SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;
4  DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;
5  FILE_NAME = vir_c2e_C3S9LOW.r02.sasf;
6  APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2018-216T23:00:00.000;
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2018-244T05:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2018-185T06:45:52.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_c2e_C3S9LOW.r02;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT    DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR   sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE       Wed Jul 04 06:45:52 2018
20 *SEQGEN     V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN      2018-216T23:00:00.000
22 *CUTOFF     2018-244T05:00:00.000
23 *TITLE      VIR_C2E_DA944_ds668
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *C2E_PERIAP_063, 2018-230T20:17:29.000
26 *C2E_PERIAP_064, 2018-231T23:31:02.000
27 *C2E_PERIAP_065, 2018-233T02:44:18.000
28 *C2E_PERIAP_066, 2018-234T05:57:21.000
29 *C2E_PERIAP_067, 2018-235T09:10:20.000
30 *C2E_PLAYBACK_067, 2018-235T13:10:00.000
31 *EPOCHS_END
32 *Input files used:
33 *File Type Last modified      File name
34 *****
35 $$EOH
36 $$EOD
37
38 request(VIR_C2E_VMLSTART_C3S9LOW,
39         START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_063-03:08:15,
40         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_c2e_C3S9LOW (ds668)",
41         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
42         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
43         KEY, "No_Key")
44
45     activity(1,
46         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
47
48         SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE", "ds668", "ds668.mc
49         fb04")
50     ),
51     note(1,
52         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
53         TEXT,\ "BEGIN SEQUENCE: ds668 - vir_c2e_C3S9LOW"\
54     ),
55 end;
56

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```
55 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOn_063,  
56     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_063-03:07:15,  
57     TITLE, "VIR Power on",  
58     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
59     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
60     KEY, "No_Key")  
61  
62     spawn(1,  
63         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
64         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\  
65         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")  
66     ),  
67     note(1,  
68         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
69         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOn_063: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\  
70     ),  
71 end;  
72  
73 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_063,  
74     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_063-02:57:15,  
75     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",  
76     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
77     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
78     KEY, "No_Key")  
79  
80     command(1,  
81         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
82         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_063: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
83         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
84     ),  
85     command(2,  
86         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
87         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_063: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\  
88         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)  
89     ),  
90     note(1,  
91         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
92         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_063: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour  
93         waiting."\  
94     ),  
95 end;  
96 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9OpenCover_063,  
97     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_063+00:03:45,  
98     TITLE, "VIR open cover",  
99     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
100    PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
101    KEY, "No_Key")  
102  
103    activity(1,  
104        SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
105        NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9OpenCover_063: Set for opening the cover."\  
106        VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")  
107    ),  
108 end;  
109  
110 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_063,
```

```
111     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_063+00:05:45,
112     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
113     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
114     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
115     KEY, "No_Key")
116
117     command(1,
118     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
119     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_063: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
120     frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,
121     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
122     ),
123     command(2,
124     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
125     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
126     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_063: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
127     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
128     ),
129     command(3,
130     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
131     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_063: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
132     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
133     ),
134     note(1,
135     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
136     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_063: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit"\
137     ),
138
139     request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CloseCover_063,
140     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_063+00:22:50,
141     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
142     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
143     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
144     KEY, "No_Key")
145
146     activity(1,
147     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
148     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CloseCover_063: Set for closing the cover.""\,
149     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
150     ),
151     end;
152
153     request(VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0ff_063,
154     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_063+00:24:50,
155     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
156     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
157     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
158     KEY, "No_Key")
159
160     command(1,
161     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
162     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0ff_063: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
163     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
164     ),
165     command(2,
166     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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167     NTEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_063: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
168     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\",75,2500)
169 ),
170     note(1,
171         SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:01\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
172         TEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_063: the cryocooling is off.\"\\
173     ),
174 end;
175
176 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_063,
177     START_TIME, C2E_PERIAP_063+00:25:50,
178     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
179     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
180     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
181     KEY, \"No_Key\")
182
183     command(1,
184         SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:00\\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
185         COMMENT, \"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\\,
186         NTEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_063: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
187         VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
188     ),
189     command(2,
190         SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:59:54\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
191         NTEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_063: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
192         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
193     ),
194     note(1,
195         SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:05\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
196         TEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_063: data volume in VR4 0.350 Gibit.\"\\
197     ),
198 end;
199
200 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_063,
201     START_TIME, C2E_PERIAP_063+01:25:50,
202     TITLE, \"VIR Power off\",
203     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
204     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
205     KEY, \"No_Key\")
206
207     note(1,
208         SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:00\\, FROM_REQUEST_START,
209         TEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_063: Power off VIR instrument.\"\\
210     ),
211     spawn(1,
212         SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:00:01\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
213         REQ_ENGINE_ID, \\ANY_ENGINE\\,
214         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
215     ),
216     note(2,
217         SCHEDULED_TIME, \\00:04:58\\, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
218         TEXT, \"VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_063: Power off VML sequence is finished;\"\\
219     ),
220 end;
221
222 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOn_064,
223     START_TIME, C2E_PERIAP_064-03:42:15,
```

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224     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
225     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
226     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
227     KEY, "No_Key")
228
229     spawn(1,
230         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
231         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
232         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
233     ),
234     note(1,
235         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
236         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Power0n_064: Power on VML sequence is finished;"\
237     ),
238 end;
239
240 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_064,
241     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_064-03:32:15,
242     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
243     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
244     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
245     KEY, "No_Key")
246
247     command(1,
248         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
249         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_064: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
250         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
251     ),
252     command(2,
253         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
254         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_064: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.""\,
255         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
256     ),
257     note(1,
258         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
259         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_064: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
260         waiting.""\
261     ),
262 end;
263 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CalibrationDump_064,
264     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_064-00:31:15,
265     TITLE, "VIR full calibration sequence",
266     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
267     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
268     KEY, "No_Key")
269
270     command(1,
271         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
272         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CalibrationDump_064: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY" "\,
273         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
274     ),
275     command(2,
276         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
277         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CalibrationDump_064: perform the internal full calibration" "\,
278         VIR_CALIBRATION("H_SPE_H_SPA_F","CLOSECOVERATEND","FULLCALSEQ")
279     ),

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280     command(3,
281         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
282         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CalibrationDump_064: select VIR on 1553 bus"\,
283         XB_SELECT_INSTRUMENT("VIR")
284     ),
285     command(4,
286         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:02\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
287         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CalibrationDump_064: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
288         VIR_MM_DUMP("NO_COMPRESSION")
289     ),
290     command(5,
291         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:15:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
292         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CalibrationDump_064: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
293         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
294     ),
295     note(1,
296         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
297         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CalibrationDump_064: full calibration is finished."\\
298     ),
299     note(2,
300         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
301         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CalibrationDump_064: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit, 120 pages, 15960
302         packets."\\
303     ),
304 end;
305 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9OpenCover_064,
306     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_064+00:03:45,
307     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
308     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
309     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
310     KEY, "No_Key")
311
312 activity(1,
313     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
314     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9OpenCover_064: Set for opening the cover."\\,
315     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
316 ),
317 end;
318
319 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_064,
320     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_064+00:05:45,
321     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
322     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
323     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
324     KEY, "No_Key")
325
326 command(1,
327     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
328     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_064: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
329     frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\\,
330     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
331 ),
332 command(2,
333     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
334     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\\,
335     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_064: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,

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```
335     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
336   ),
337   command(3,
338     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
339     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_064: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
340     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
341   ),
342   note(1,
343     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
344     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_064: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit" \
345   ),
346 end;
347
348 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CloseCover_064,
349   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_064+00:22:50,
350   TITLE, "VIR close cover",
351   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
352   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
353   KEY, "No_Key")
354
355   activity(1,
356     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
357     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CloseCover_064: Set for closing the cover." \,
358     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
359   ),
360 end;
361
362 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_064,
363   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_064+00:24:50,
364   TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
365   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
366   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
367   KEY, "No_Key")
368
369   command(1,
370     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
371     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_064: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
372     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
373   ),
374   command(2,
375     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
376     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_064: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime." \,
377     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
378   ),
379   note(1,
380     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
381     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_064: the cryocooling is off." \
382   ),
383 end;
384
385 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_064,
386   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_064+00:25:50,
387   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
388   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
389   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
390   KEY, "No_Key")
391
```

```
392     command(1,
393         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
394         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\\,
395         NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_064: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
396         VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
397     ),
398     command(2,
399         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
400         NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_064: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
401         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
402     ),
403     note(1,
404         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
405         TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_064: data volume in VR4 0.826 Gibit.\"\\
406     ),
407 end;
408
409 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_064,
410     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_064+01:25:50,
411     TITLE, \"VIR Power off\",
412     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
413     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
414     KEY, \"No_Key\")
415
416     note(1,
417         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
418         TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_064: Power off VIR instrument.\"\\
419     ),
420     spawn(1,
421         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
422         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\\,
423         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
424     ),
425     note(2,
426         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
427         TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_064: Power off VML sequence is finished;\"\\
428     ),
429 end;
430
431 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOn_065,
432     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_065-03:06:30,
433     TITLE, \"VIR Power on\",
434     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
435     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
436     KEY, \"No_Key\")
437
438     spawn(1,
439         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
440         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\\,
441         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,\"VIR_P\",\"SAFE\")
442     ),
443     note(1,
444         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
445         TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOn_065: Power on VML sequence is finished;\"\\
446     ),
447 end;
448
```

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449 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_065,
450     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_065-02:56:30,
451     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
452     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
453     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
454     KEY, "No_Key")
455
456     command(1,
457         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
458         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_065: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
459         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
460     ),
461     command(2,
462         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
463         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_065: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN.\",
464         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
465     ),
466     note(1,
467         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
468         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_065: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
469         waiting."\
470     ),
471 end;
472
472 request(VIR_C2E_C3S90penCover_065,
473     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_065+00:04:30,
474     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
475     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
476     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
477     KEY, "No_Key")
478
479     activity(1,
480         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
481         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S90penCover_065: Set for opening the cover.\",
482         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
483     ),
484 end;
485
486 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_065,
487     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_065+00:06:30,
488     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
489     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
490     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
491     KEY, "No_Key")
492
493     command(1,
494         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
495         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_065: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
496         frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,
497         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
498     ),
499     command(2,
500         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
501         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
502         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_065: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
503         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
504     ),

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504     command(3,  
505         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
506         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_065: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
507         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
508     ),  
509     note(1,  
510         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
511         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_065: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit\"\\  
512     ),  
513 end;  
514  
515 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CloseCover_065,  
516     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_065+00:23:35,  
517     TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",  
518     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
519     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
520     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
521  
522     activity(1,  
523         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
524         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9CloseCover_065: Set for closing the cover.\"\\,  
525         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")  
526     ),  
527 end;  
528  
529 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_065,  
530     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_065+00:25:05,  
531     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",  
532     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
533     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
534     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
535  
536     command(1,  
537         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
538         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_065: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
539         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
540     ),  
541     command(2,  
542         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
543         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_065: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,  
544         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\",75,2500)  
545     ),  
546     note(1,  
547         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
548         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_065: the cryocooling is off.\"\\  
549     ),  
550 end;  
551  
552 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_065,  
553     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_065+00:26:05,  
554     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",  
555     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
556     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
557     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
558  
559     command(1,  
560         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
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561 COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000\"\\,
562 NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_065: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
563 VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
564 ),
565 command(2,
566 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:59:54\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
567 NTEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_065: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
568 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
569 ),
570 note(1,
571 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
572 TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_065: data volume in VR4 1.176 Gibit.\"\\
573 ),
574 end;
575
576 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_065,
577 START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_065+01:26:05,
578 TITLE, \"VIR Power off\",
579 REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
580 PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
581 KEY, \"No_Key\")
582
583 note(1,
584 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:00\",FROM_REQUEST_START,
585 TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_065: Power off VIR instrument.\"\\
586 ),
587 spawn(1,
588 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:01\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
589 REQ_ENGINE_ID,\"ANY_ENGINE\",
590 RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
591 ),
592 note(2,
593 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:04:58\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
594 TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_065: Power off VML sequence is finished;\"\\
595 ),
596 end;
597
598 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOn_066,
599 START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_066-03:06:30,
600 TITLE, \"VIR Power on\",
601 REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
602 PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
603 KEY, \"No_Key\")
604
605 spawn(1,
606 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:00\",FROM_REQUEST_START,
607 REQ_ENGINE_ID,\"ANY_ENGINE\",
608 RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,\"VIR_P\",\"SAFE\")
609 ),
610 note(1,
611 SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:07:00\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
612 TEXT,\"VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOn_066: Power on VML sequence is finished;\"\\
613 ),
614 end;
615
616 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOn_066,
617 START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_066-02:56:30,
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618     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
619     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
620     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
621     KEY, "No_Key")
622
623     command(1,
624         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
625         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_066: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
626         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
627     ),
628     command(2,
629         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
630         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_066: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\,
631         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
632     ),
633     note(1,
634         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
635         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_066: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
        waiting."\
636     ),
637 end;
638
639 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9OpenCover_066,
640     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_066+00:04:30,
641     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
642     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
643     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
644     KEY, "No_Key")
645
646     activity(1,
647         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
648         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9OpenCover_066: Set for opening the cover."\,
649         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
650     ),
651 end;
652
653 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_066,
654     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_066+00:06:30,
655     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
656     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
657     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
658     KEY, "No_Key")
659
660     command(1,
661         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
662         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_066: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
        frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s"\,
663         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195, "IR_ONLY", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 10, "NO_VI
664     ),
665     command(2,
666         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
667         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000"\,
668         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_066: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
669         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
670     ),
671     command(3,
672         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
    
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673     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_066: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,  
674     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
675   ),  
676   note(1,  
677     SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:00:05 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
678     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_066: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit" \,  
679   ),  
680 end;  
681  
682 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CloseCover_066,  
683   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_066+00:23:35,  
684   TITLE, "VIR close cover",  
685   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
686   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
687   KEY, "No_Key")  
688  
689   activity(1,  
690     SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:00:00 \, FROM_REQUEST_START,  
691     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CloseCover_066: Set for closing the cover." \,  
692     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")  
693   ),  
694 end;  
695  
696 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_066,  
697   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_066+00:25:05,  
698   TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",  
699   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
700   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
701   KEY, "No_Key")  
702  
703   command(1,  
704     SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:00:00 \, FROM_REQUEST_START,  
705     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_066: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,  
706     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
707   ),  
708   command(2,  
709     SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:00:05 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
710     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_066: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime." \,  
711     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)  
712   ),  
713   note(1,  
714     SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:00:01 \, FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
715     TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_066: the cryocooling is off." \,  
716   ),  
717 end;  
718  
719 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_066,  
720   START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_066+00:26:05,  
721   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
722   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
723   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
724   KEY, "No_Key")  
725  
726   command(1,  
727     SCHEDULED_TIME,\ 00:00:00 \, FROM_REQUEST_START,  
728     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000" \,  
729     NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_066: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
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730     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
731     ),
732     command(2,
733         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
734         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_066: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
735         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
736     ),
737     note(1,
738         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
739         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_066: data volume in VR4 1.526 Gibit." \
740     ),
741 end;
742
743 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_066,
744     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_066+01:26:05,
745     TITLE, "VIR Power off",
746     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
747     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
748     KEY, "No_Key")
749
750     note(1,
751         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
752         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_066: Power off VIR instrument." \
753     ),
754     spawn(1,
755         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
756         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
757         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)
758     ),
759     note(2,
760         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
761         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_066: Power off VML sequence is finished;" \
762     ),
763 end;
764
765 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOn_067,
766     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_067-03:06:30,
767     TITLE, "VIR Power on",
768     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
769     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
770     KEY, "No_Key")
771
772     spawn(1,
773         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
774         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
775         RT_on_board_block(vpon_vir_power_on,"VIR_P","SAFE")
776     ),
777     note(1,
778         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:07:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
779         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOn_067: Power on VML sequence is finished;" \
780     ),
781 end;
782
783 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOn_067,
784     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_067-02:56:30,
785     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
786     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",

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787     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
788     KEY, "No_Key")
789
790     command(1,
791         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
792         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_067: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
793         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
794     ),
795     command(2,
796         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
797         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_067: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN." \,
798         VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",85,0)
799     ),
800     note(1,
801         SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:45:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
802         TEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9Cryocooler0n_067: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
            waiting." \
803     ),
804 end;
805
806 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9OpenCover_067,
807     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_067+00:04:30,
808     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
809     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
810     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
811     KEY, "No_Key")
812
813     activity(1,
814         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
815         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9OpenCover_067: Set for opening the cover." \,
816         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
817     ),
818 end;
819
820 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_067,
821     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_067+00:06:30,
822     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
823     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
824     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
825     KEY, "No_Key")
826
827     command(1,
828         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
829         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_067: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,1 detector,195
            frame,5 RepTime,Integration time IR=2.500s VIS=0.020s" \,
830         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",5,63,125,5,1,67,195,"IR_ONLY","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
831     ),
832     command(2,
833         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
834         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=1.000" \,
835         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_067: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
836         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
837     ),
838     command(3,
839         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:16:51\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
840         NTEXT,\ "VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_067: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
841         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()

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842     ),
843     note(1,
844         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
845         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9PushbroomToVIR_067: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.339 Gibit"\
846     ),
847 end;
848
849 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CloseCover_067,
850     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_067+00:23:35,
851     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
852     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
853     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
854     KEY, "No_Key")
855
856 activity(1,
857     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
858     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9CloseCover_067: Set for closing the cover."\,
859     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
860     ),
861 end;
862
863 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_067,
864     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_067+00:25:05,
865     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
866     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
867     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
868     KEY, "No_Key")
869
870 command(1,
871     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
872     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_067: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
873     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
874     ),
875 command(2,
876     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
877     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_067: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime."\,
878     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
879     ),
880 note(1,
881     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
882     TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9CryocoolerOff_067: the cryocooling is off."\
883     ),
884 end;
885
886 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_067,
887     START_TIME,C2E_PERIAP_067+00:26:05,
888     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
889     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
890     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
891     KEY, "No_Key")
892
893 command(1,
894     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
895     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_FACTOR=1.000"\,
896     NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_067: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
897     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
898     ),
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899     command(2,  
900         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:59:54\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
901         NTEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_067: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
902         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
903     ),  
904     note(1,  
905         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
906         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9DumpDataToVR4_067: data volume in VR4 1.877 Gibit.\"\\  
907     ),  
908 end;  
909  
910 request(VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_067,  
911     START_TIME,C2E_PLAYBACK_067-00:10:00,  
912     TITLE, \"VIR Power off\",  
913     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
914     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
915     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
916  
917     note(1,  
918         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
919         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_067: Power off VIR instrument.\"\\  
920     ),  
921     spawn(1,  
922         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
923         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\\,  
924         RT_on_board_block(vpof_vir_power_off)  
925     ),  
926     note(2,  
927         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:04:58\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
928         TEXT,\\"VIR_C2E_C3S9PowerOff_067: Power off VML sequence is finished;\"\\  
929     ),  
930 end;  
931  
932 request(VIR_C2E_VMLEND_C3S9LOW,  
933     START_TIME,C2E_PLAYBACK_067-00:04:00,  
934     TITLE, \"VIR Sequence End - vir_c2e_c3s9LOW (ds668)\",  
935     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",  
936     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",  
937     KEY, \"No_Key\")  
938  
939     note(1,  
940         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
941         TEXT,\\"END OF SEQUENCE: ds668 - vir_c2e_c3s9LOW\"\\  
942     ),  
943 end;  
944  
945 $$EOF
```